

Historical Volatility vs Implied Volatility

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1 Introduction

In every quantitative model of an asset price, two components determine its dynamics: a deterministic drift term and a stochastic volatility term. The drift, or trend, represents the expected average direction of the asset; for example, this may correspond to a long-term upward trajectory or to cyclical behaviour, depending on the data and the chosen specification. Because the drift is highly sensitive to the sample period and modelling choices, its estimation is often subjective. The stochastic component, volatility, measures the random deviations from this trend. It governs the magnitude of fluctuations in asset prices and is directly linked to the risk borne by investors. In share and derivatives markets, volatility plays a central role: higher volatility implies a wider distribution of possible outcomes for an asset, which translates into greater uncertainty in the valuation of options. As such, volatility estimation is the cornerstone of both risk management and derivative pricing. Beyond derivative markets, volatility is also critical in applications such as portfolio allocation (choosing how to distribute capital across different assets), Value-at-Risk (VaR) calculations (estimating the worst-case loss of a portfolio at a chosen confidence level), and stress testing (assessing the resilience of financial systems under extreme market scenarios).

To study volatility, a model of asset price dynamics must first be specified. The choice of model is crucial because the decomposition into drift and volatility is not unique: a more refined drift specification can capture more systematic movements of the asset, leaving a smaller residual volatility term to represent only the truly random fluctuations. Conversely, if the drift is oversimplified, volatility will appear larger because it must compensate for unmodelled systematic behaviour. In this project, we adopt the geometric Brownian motion (GBM) model. GBM is widely used because it captures several stylised facts of financial markets: asset prices remain strictly positive, volatility scales with both time and price, and log returns are approximately normally distributed over short horizons (days to weeks). At the same time, GBM has important shortcomings. It does not capture volatility clustering, which is addressed by ARCH/GARCH models, nor sudden jumps, which are better described by jump-diffusion processes. Despite these limitations, GBM is a natural starting point because it admits an analytical solution and serves as the foundation of other financial tools such as Black-Scholes equation (used to price options).

Two main approaches to estimating volatility are considered in this report: historical volatility and implied volatility. Historical volatility is backward-looking, relying on past price observations under the real-world probability measure \mathbb{P} . Implied volatility is forward-looking, inferred from option prices under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{Q} , and incorporates both the market's expectations and a volatility risk premium. The choice between them depends on data availability, market conditions, computational capacity and the intended application.

Our aim in this project is to examine how these two methods are formulated, evaluate their modeling assumptions and numerical errors, and identify the contexts in which each offers the most reliable insight. We also discuss adaptations that can enhance their robustness in practice.

2 Historical Volatility

The historical method for approximating volatility is conceptually straightforward, as it relies on the sample variance as an unbiased estimator of the underlying volatility. In essence, this approach uses the variability observed in a sample of stock price changes to estimate the variance of the distribution that generates those changes.

The method begins by assuming that the stock price follows a lognormal random walk, expressed as

$$\frac{dS_i}{S_i} = \mu dt + \sigma\sqrt{dt}\varphi_i, \quad (1)$$

where S_i is the stock price at time $t = i$, μ is a constant drift term (deterministic trend), σ is the volatility (stochastic component), and $\varphi_i \sim N(0, 1)$ is a standard normal random variable. Equation (1) is a special case of an Itô process, given by

$$dS_t = a(S_t, t) dt + b(S_t, t) dW_t,$$

whose solution can be obtained by applying Itô's Lemma:

$$df = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + a \frac{\partial f}{\partial S} + \frac{1}{2} b^2 \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial S^2} \right) dt + b \frac{\partial f}{\partial S} dW_t. \quad (2)$$

Substituting $f = \ln S$ into equation (2) yields the solution to equation (1):

$$S_t = S_0 \exp \left[\left(\mu - \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \right) t + \sigma \sqrt{t} \varphi \right].$$

Taking logarithms and rearranging gives

$$\ln S_t - \ln S_0 = \left(\mu - \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \right) t + \sigma \sqrt{t} \varphi,$$

demonstrating that the log of the stock price is normally distributed,

$$\ln S_t - \ln S_0 \sim N \left(\left(\mu - \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \right) t, \sigma^2 t \right).$$

Given a time series of stock prices $\mathbf{S} = (S_0, S_1, \dots, S_n)$, we define the log changes

$$W_i = \ln S_i - \ln S_{i-1}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n.$$

These changes W_i are independent and identically distributed with

$$W_i \sim N \left(\mu - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}, \sigma^2 \right).$$

An unbiased estimator for σ^2 can then be obtained using the sample variance, expressed as

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \text{var}(W) = E[W^2] - (E[W])^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n W_i^2 - \frac{1}{n^2-n} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n W_i \right)^2. \quad (3)$$

Finally, when applying this method, it is essential to consider the time units used for t . If t is measured in days, then $\hat{\sigma}^2$ estimates the daily variance. To convert this to annualised volatility (used for option pricing), the estimate is scaled by the square root of the number of trading days in a year (typically 252):

$$\hat{\sigma}_{\text{yearly}} = \sqrt{252} \hat{\sigma}_{\text{daily}}.$$

2.1 Example

To illustrate this method and validate the code computing historical volatility, we will take a simple example: $\mathbf{S} = (1, 2, 5)$ which were taken over consecutive days. Then $\mathbf{W} = (0.6931, 0.9163)$ and using equation (3) we have that $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{daily}}^2 = 0.0249$ which leads to $\hat{\sigma}_{\text{yearly}} = 2.50$. The code that computes this is given in appendix 5.1.

2.2 Error Analysis

While this method is simple, there are a multitude of limitations that should be considered when implementing it. The majority of these arise from the modeling assumptions associated with using the lognormal random walk, which include constant drift, constant volatility, no dividends, and uncorrelated returns.

2.2.1 Modelling Assumptions

The first assumption is that σ is constant. This contradicts observations such as volatility clustering, where periods of high volatility tend to be followed by periods of high volatility, and periods of low volatility by low volatility. This phenomenon can occur when investors react similarly to news, mimicing each other's trades and causing a short burst in trading activity accompanied by a spike in volatility. Such bursts may trigger further reactions, sustaining elevated volatility levels. By using shorter time windows we reduce the period over which volatility may change significantly. However, this workaround comes at a cost, as

$$\text{var}(\hat{\sigma}^2) = \frac{2\sigma^4}{n-1},$$

which indicates that the precision of the estimator improves with the number of data points used. Estimating volatility from historical data therefore involves a compromise between using enough data points to reduce estimator uncertainty and limiting the sample period to avoid capturing non-constant volatility.

Another modeling assumption is that μ is constant. While this may be reasonable in periods of economic stability, it often fails during times of external shocks, such as policy changes, or internal shifts, such as changes in company leadership. Similar to the assumption of constant volatility, mitigating against drift variability requires reducing the sample time frame, which again reduces the accuracy of the estimator.

We have already discussed the limitations of using independent normal increments in stock returns in the context of correlated volatilities (volatility clustering). However, another issue is that lognormal walks fail to capture jumps in stock prices. This is less problematic during calm trading days but becomes significant during sudden news events, geopolitical shocks, or financial crises.

The final limitation considered here is that the model does not include dividend payments. While this is less problematic when dividend yields are low or when profits are reinvested, it becomes more significant for mature companies where dividends are not typically reinvested. One way to include dividends in the continuous model is to replace the μ term with $(\mu - q)$, where q represents the dividend yield. This approach assumes that dividends are paid continuously, whereas in reality they are distributed in discrete amounts.

These limitations mean that the method of historical volatility loses its viability in contexts where the limitations are violated as is likely the case for real world option trading.

2.2.2 Numerical Error

Fortunately, stock data is typically very rich, with prices often recorded multiple times per second. This allows for the construction of time series for different parameters to verify whether they meet

the model's assumptions. These time series can be analysed using statistical tests: σ can be tested for constancy using Engle's ARCH, μ can be tested with the CUSUM or Chow tests, and the normality and independence of φ_i can be tested with the Shapiro–Wilk or Jarque–Bera tests. By adjusting the time frame until these tests are satisfied, one can, in theory, estimate volatility over a given interval with greater confidence.

Another advantage of this methodology is its numerical stability. Most of the numerical error arises from roundoff errors when subtracting numbers of similar magnitude. Using the sample variance in the form given by equation (3), instead of the naive deviation formula

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (W_i - \bar{W})^2,$$

reduces the risk of accumulating roundoff errors when W_i are close in value to \bar{W} . Additionally, if S_i and S_{i-1} are similar in size, roundoff errors in the definition of W_i can be reduced by writing

$$W_i = \ln S_i - \ln S_{i-1} = \ln \left(\frac{S_i}{S_{i-1}} \right).$$

For very large datasets, one may also consider Welford's algorithm, which is even more numerically robust and spatially efficient, as it updates the variance incrementally with each new data point.

3 Implied Volatility

The concept of implied volatility rests on the principle that, under the Black–Scholes framework for European-style options (options exercisable only at expiry), the option price is determined uniquely by the following parameters: the risk-free interest rate r , the volatility of the underlying asset σ , the time to maturity T , and the strike price X . Conversely, if we observe r , T , X , and the market option price V_0 , there exists a unique implied volatility σ^* consistent with that price. Since no closed-form inversion exists for σ^* in the Black–Scholes formula, the implied volatility must be computed numerically. The typical procedure is to guess a volatility, σ , compute the corresponding option price $V_0(\sigma)$, and compare it with the market-observed price $V_0(\sigma^*)$. The discrepancy is then used to update the guess until $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*$. This transforms the problem into a root-finding procedure.

3.1 Option Pricing Framework

The modern theory of option pricing begins with the risk-neutral valuation formula:

$$V_0 = e^{-rT} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T] = e^{-rT} \int_0^\infty f_{S_T}(S) V_T(S) dS, \quad (4)$$

where $f_{S_T}(S)$ is the probability density function of the terminal asset price S_T under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{Q} (a direct consequence of the no-arbitrage principle).

An alternative but equivalent approach is via the celebrated Black–Scholes partial differential equation (PDE):

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial S^2} + rS \frac{\partial V}{\partial S} - rV = 0.$$

With an appropriate change of variables,

$$x = \ln \left(\frac{S_0}{X} \right), \quad y = \ln \left(\frac{S_T}{X} \right), \quad (5)$$

this PDE reduces to the classical heat equation. Solving it subject to the terminal condition $V_T = \text{payoff}(S)$ and the boundary conditions $V_t(S) \rightarrow 0$ as $S_t \rightarrow 0$, and $V_t(S) \rightarrow S_t - X e^{-r(T-t)}$

as $S_t \rightarrow \infty$, yields the integral representation

$$\begin{aligned}
V_0(x) &= A(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} B(x, y) V_T(y) dy, \\
\text{where } A(x) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\sigma^2\pi T}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}kx - \frac{1}{8}\sigma^2k^2T - rT\right), \\
B(x, y) &= \exp\left(-\frac{(x-y)^2}{2\sigma^2T} + \frac{1}{2}ky\right), \\
k &= \frac{2r}{\sigma^2} - 1.
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

This formulation mirrors the risk-neutral expectation in equation (4), with $B(x, y)$ playing the role of a transformed probability density for the payoff.

3.2 Numerical Integration: Composite Simpson's Rule

The integral in equation (6) cannot, in general, be solved analytically, so numerical approximation is required. A robust choice is Composite Simpson's $\frac{1}{3}$ Rule. This method partitions the integration interval into subintervals, and within each, constructs a quadratic interpolant based on the function values at the endpoints and midpoint. By piecing together these interpolants, one obtains an approximation of the full integral.

The formula for Composite Simpson's $\frac{1}{3}$ Rule is

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_a^b f(y) dy &\approx \frac{h}{3} \left[f(a) + 2 \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{2}-1} f(x_{2i}) + 4 \sum_{i=1}^{\frac{n}{2}} f(x_{2i-1}) + f(b) \right], \\
\text{where } x_i &= a + ih \quad \text{and} \quad h = \frac{b-a}{n}.
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Note that with this notation, h refers to the stepsize between a subinterval boundary and its midpoint. Since each subinterval has a midpoint, n must be even.

Illustrative Example

To validate the implementation of Simpson's rule, consider the simple integral

$$I = \int_0^1 X e^{-r\sigma T} e^{Ty} dy, \tag{8}$$

with constants $X = 10$, $r = 0.05$, $\sigma = 0.1$, and $T = 0.5$.

The analytic solution is

$$I = \frac{X e^{-r\sigma T}}{T} (e^T - 1) \approx 12.9420298618 \dots$$

Comparisons of the numerical result with this analytic benchmark, including error behaviour as a function of step size, are reported in Figure 1. As expected, the error decays as $\mathcal{O}(h^4)$, consistent with Simpson's method being a fourth-order scheme (superior to the trapezoidal rule, which is only second-order).

The total error for composite Simpson's rule has two main components:

$$\text{total error} = \text{truncation error} + \text{roundoff error} = K_1 h^4 + \frac{K_2}{h},$$

for constants K_1 and K_2 depending on the function being integrated and the machine precision. The truncation error for Simpson's rule is given in general form by

$$\text{truncation error} = -\frac{(b-a)}{180} h^4 f^{(4)}(\xi), \quad \xi \in [a, b].$$

For the integrand in (8), this becomes

$$\text{truncation error} = -T^4 X e^{-r\sigma T} e^{T\xi} \frac{(b-a)}{180} h^4,$$

$$\xi \in [0, 1].$$

Since $T > 0$, the exponential $e^{T\xi}$ is increasing on $[0, 1]$, so the maximum occurs at $\xi = 1$. Thus an explicit upper bound is

$$|\text{truncation error}| \leq T^4 X e^{T(1-r\sigma)} \frac{(b-a)}{180} h^4. \quad (9)$$

Suppose we require 6-digit accuracy. Then the total relative error must be below 0.5×10^{-7} . Since the exact integral value is approximately 12.9420298618, this corresponds to a maximum allowable absolute error of about

$$12.9420298618 \times 0.5 \times 10^{-7} \approx 3 \times 10^{-8}.$$

Assuming truncation error dominates (i.e. for sufficiently large h before roundoff effects become significant), equation (9) can be rearranged to solve for the minimum step size h needed to guarantee this accuracy. For the chosen parameters, the estimate gives a required $h \approx 7.2 \times 10^{-1}$.

Figure 1 confirms that this theoretical estimate agrees well with the empirical error observed from the code.

3.3 Root-Finding for Implied Volatility

We now return to the implied volatility problem. Given a market option price $V_0(\sigma^*)$, we define the residual function

$$\phi(\sigma) = V_0(\sigma) - V_0(\sigma^*). \quad (10)$$

The task of finding σ^* is thus equivalent to solving the root-finding problem $\phi(\sigma) = 0$.

A suitable algorithm is the Newton–Secant method, where successive iterates are updated according to

$$\sigma_{n+1} = \sigma_n - \phi(\sigma_n) \frac{\sigma_n - \sigma_{n-1}}{\phi(\sigma_n) - \phi(\sigma_{n-1})}. \quad (10)$$

The iteration proceeds until $|\phi(\sigma)|$ falls below a prescribed tolerance, or the sequence fails to converge. If convergence is achieved, the final iterate is taken as the implied volatility.

3.4 Sources of Error

The method of implied volatility has several sources of error, both modelling and numerical. In this section we discuss these in more detail and outline possible ways of reducing their impact.

3.4.1 Modelling Assumptions

The option pricing formula in equation (6) was derived from the Black–Scholes PDE, which itself assumes that the underlying asset follows a lognormal diffusion. Consequently, the method of implied volatility inherits the same structural limitations as historical volatility. The Black–Scholes framework also assumes: the existence of a constant risk-free rate r , no arbitrage opportunities,

Variation of absolute error against step size on tester function when using Simpson's Composite 1/3 rule

Figure 1: Log–log plot of the absolute numerical error against step size when computing equation (8) with $X = 10$, $r = 0.05$, $\sigma = 0.1$ and $T = 0.5$.

and a frictionless market.

The assumption of a risk-free interest rate is reasonable in developed markets such as the United States, where short-term Treasury bills approximate risk-free assets. However, in emerging markets, or in cases where government bonds pay coupons that are not immediately reinvested, the assumption breaks down.

The requirement that markets are arbitrage-free means that there is no possibility of generating a riskless profit without investment. This is approximately satisfied in highly liquid markets where arbitrage opportunities are quickly exploited. The assumption of a frictionless market (no transaction costs, unlimited short selling, infinitely divisible assets, continuous trading) is of course unrealistic, but is often a good approximation in liquid, developed markets where transaction costs are negligible relative to price fluctuations.

3.4.2 Root-Finding Error: Secant vs Newton–Raphson

Another source of error arises in the parameter-solving stage. The Newton–Secant method for root-finding requires two initial guesses for σ . A natural alternative is the Newton–Raphson method, which updates according to

$$\sigma_{n+1} = \sigma_n - \frac{\phi(\sigma_n)}{\phi'(\sigma_n)}. \quad (11)$$

This has quadratic convergence (faster than the superlinear rate of the secant method, which has order of convergence equal to the golden ratio). Moreover, Newton–Raphson requires only a single initial guess. The derivative of the residual function is

$$\phi'(\sigma) = \frac{\partial V_0(\sigma)}{\partial \sigma} = \nu_0,$$

where

$$\nu_0 = A(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} B(x, y) V_T(y) \left[\frac{-1 + (k+1)x}{\sigma} + \frac{T\sigma}{4} k(k+2) + \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{(x-y)^2}{T\sigma^2} - (k+1)y \right) \right] dy.$$

If the bulk of computation time lies in evaluating the integrals, then each Newton–Raphson step is roughly twice as expensive as a secant step (since both $\phi(\sigma)$ and $\phi'(\sigma)$ must be computed, compared with only $\phi(\sigma)$ in the secant method if integrals are stored). Appendix 5.4 shows that, even accounting for faster convergence, the secant method can be faster overall in this problem. The disadvantage remains that poor initial guesses can cause divergence. Several strategies help mitigate this risk:

- **Monotonicity insight.** From equation (4), the only dependence on σ is through the risk-neutral density $f_{S_T}(S)$. Increasing σ flattens the density, which raises the option value. Thus, if a trial σ produces too high an option price, the next guess must be smaller, and vice versa.
- **Historical volatility as a starting point.** Although not guaranteed to be close, historical volatility estimates can provide useful initial guesses, especially when bid–ask spreads are tight.
- **Parameter continuation.** If a system with parameters k has known implied volatility σ , then σ can be used as a starting guess for nearby parameters $k + \Delta k$. Using asymptotic Black–Scholes formulae, when $S_0 = X$, $r = 0$, and $T \ll 1$,

$$\sigma \approx \frac{C_0 \sqrt{2\pi}}{S_0 \sqrt{T}} \quad \text{or} \quad \sigma \approx \frac{(S_0 - P_0) \sqrt{2\pi}}{S_0 \sqrt{T}}$$

for call and put prices respectively. These can serve as initial guesses, with subsequent updates as parameters are perturbed.

3.4.3 Market Price Ambiguity

A further complication is the choice of market price. In practice, identical options can be transacted at different prices, leading to different implied volatilities. Which of these is the “correct” implied volatility?

In efficient markets, mispriced options are quickly arbitrated away: If the implied volatility is too high, the option price is inflated and shorting becomes profitable. If it is too low, buying the option is profitable.

Thus, incorrectly priced options vanish quickly, and the remaining distribution of implied volatilities can be assumed to cluster around the true value. An unbiased estimator is therefore the sample mean:

$$\hat{\sigma}^* = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i^*.$$

A more robust approach uses weights w_i :

$$\hat{\sigma}^* = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \sigma_i^*, \quad \sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1,$$

with w_i reflecting trade reliability. A simple weighting scheme is proportional to trade volume:

$$w_i = \frac{v_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n v_j}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n,$$

where v_i is the volume of the i^{th} trade.

This can be extended across time to estimate an average implied volatility:

$$\hat{\sigma}^*_{\text{average}} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} w_{i,j} \sigma_{i,j}^*,$$

where $\sigma_{i,j}^*$ is the j^{th} implied volatility at time $t = i$, $w_{i,j}$ is a local weight, and n_i is the number of trades at time i .

In principle, any European-style option can be used. Exchanges typically report puts, calls, and straddles; some providers also include multi-leg strategies such as spreads. For strategies with multiple strike prices, the option price is computed as a sum:

$$V_0(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n V_{0,i}(x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[A_i(x_i) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} B(x_i, y_i) V_{T,i}(y_i) dy_i \right].$$

Not every stock has a liquid options market: large companies may see heavy option trading, whereas smaller firms may have very little. Nevertheless, the advantage of using option prices is that they implicitly reflect real-world frictions such as transaction costs, dividends, coupon payments, and deviations from the risk-free rate assumption. This gives implied volatility estimates practical relevance even beyond the strict Black–Scholes setting.

3.4.4 Numerical Errors

Finally, numerical errors must be considered. We have already seen in Section 3.1 that the composite Simpson’s $\frac{1}{3}$ rule requires using stepsize to balance truncation error against roundoff error.

A further difficulty arises because the integral in equation (6) has infinite limits. In practice, these must be truncated to $[-x_{\max}, x_{\max}]$. The natural approach is to increase x_{\max} until the tails of the kernel $B(x, y)$ are negligible. However, too small a choice of x_{\max} underestimates the option price, while too large a choice increases computational cost. Careful calibration of this truncation is therefore required.

4 Conclusion

An unavoidable consideration when selecting a method for estimating volatility is the availability of input data. The historical method depends only on past stock prices, which are abundant and widely available for most traded assets. By contrast, implied volatility requires option prices, which exist only for a subset of firms with sufficiently liquid derivatives markets. Moreover, attempts to improve robustness by averaging across multiple option contracts further restrict applicability to companies with deep options markets.

Another key factor is computational stability. The historical method is numerically straightforward and stable. Even in extreme scenarios, alternatives such as Welford’s algorithm can be employed to improve robustness and reduce memory requirements. By contrast, implied volatility estimation involves numerical integration and root-finding. Accuracy requires careful tuning of step size and truncation limits, and convergence may fail without good initial guesses. Nonetheless, issues can be mitigated by directional insights (monotonicity of option value in volatility), parameter continuation techniques, and combining implied and historical volatility for starting values. Market heterogeneity in implied volatilities can also be addressed by using weighted averages based on trade volume to generate more reliable estimates.

Perhaps the most important distinction lies in what each method is actually measuring. Historical volatility quantifies past variability in stock prices, and therefore reflects the impact of realised events (e.g. elections, policy changes, or crises). Implied volatility, by contrast, is forward-looking: it encodes the market’s collective expectations of future uncertainty. Hence, historical volatility reacts to past shocks, whereas implied volatility anticipates future ones. This explains why combining implied volatilities from options with different maturities can be problematic: each contract embeds expectations about distinct horizons and event risks. Moreover, implied volatility is shaped not only by the underlying asset’s properties, but also by market sentiment and risk perception.

When comparing historical and implied volatilities at a given time, it is best to use symmetric short windows of data around the present. Even then, systematic differences remain. Markets are generally risk-averse, meaning they tend to price options as if large volatility spikes are more frequent than suggested by historical data. As a result, implied volatility tends to be persistently higher than realised historical volatility- a phenomenon often described as the volatility risk premium. Direct comparison must therefore be made with caution, since the two quantities are defined under different probability measures and capture different aspects of risk.

Finally, with respect to modelling assumptions, both methods are tied to the framework of geometric Brownian motion (and, for implied volatility, the Black–Scholes equation). Their accuracy improves when the underlying asset exhibits approximately lognormal returns, constant volatility, and no jumps. Yet in practice, both methods deviate when these assumptions fail. Implied volatility, however, often retains greater practical relevance, since it incorporates market pricing of risk and thereby reflects real-world frictions and investor sentiment.

5 Appendix

5.1

```
1 double Variance_Estimator(MVector v){
2     MVector w;
3     for (int i=1;i<v.size();i++)
4         {
5             w.push_back(std::log(v[i])-std::log(v[i-1]));
6         }
7     double sum=0, sum_of_squares=0;
8     for (int i=0;i<w.size();i++)
9         {
```

```

10     sum+=w[i];
11     sum_of_squares+=w[i]*w[i];
12 }
13 double var;
14 var=(sum_of_squares/(w.size()-1))-((sum*sum)/(w.size()*w.size()-w.size()));
15 return std::sqrt(252*var);
16 }

```

5.2

```

17 //derived test integral class
18 class Test_Integral: public Integral
19 {
20     public:
21     Test_Integral(){X=10; r=0.05; sigma=0.1;T=0.5;}
22     virtual double operator()(const double& y)
23     {
24         return X*exp(T*(y-r*sigma));
25     }
26     void SetX(double X_){X=X_;}
27     void Setr(double r_){r=r_;}
28     void Setsigma(double sigma_){sigma=sigma_;}
29     void SetT(double T_){T=T_;}
30     private:
31     double X, r, sigma, T;
32 };

```

5.3

```

33 // function to implement Simpsons rule from y=a to y=b with n steps
34 double integrate(Integral &f, double a, double b, int n)
35 {
36     if (n%2!=0 || a>b) {std::cout<<"Error"<<std::endl; return 1;}
37     double sum=0, h=(b-a)/n;
38     sum+=f(a)+f(b);
39     for (int j=1; j<=n/2-1;j++)
40     {
41         sum+=2*f(a+2*j*h)+4*f(a+(2*j-1)*h);
42     }
43     sum=(h/3)*(sum+4*f(a+(n-1)*h));
44     return sum;
45 }

```

5.4

We will show how you can compare the time required for 2 different algorithms to converge where the algorithms in question have different orders of convergence and different time requirements at each step.

A sequence converges with order p if the errors, e_n say, are satisfy

$$e_{n+1} \leq C e_n^p$$

for some constant C . If we consider the asymptotic scenario where lower order terms can be ignored, then

$$\log(e_n) \propto p^n.$$

This means that the number of steps required to guarantee convergence with a tolerance, ε say, is

$$n \approx \log_p \left[\log \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \right) \right],$$

which can be converted to

$$n \approx \frac{\ln \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{\varepsilon} \right) \right]}{\ln(p)}$$

If t_p is the time per step then the total Time is given by $T_p = nt_p$. Considering the example with a sequence converging quadratically and one with order the golden ratio, where each step with the quadratic requiring double the computation time,

$$\frac{T_2}{T_\phi} = 2 \frac{\ln \phi}{\ln 2} \approx 1.4,$$

so for the same initial guess, quadratic will converge slower for any tolerance.

5.5

```

46 #ifndef MVECTOR_H // the 'include guard'
47 #define MVECTOR_H // see C++ Primer Sec. 2.9.2
48
49 #include <vector>
50 #include <iostream>
51
52 // Class that represents a mathematical vector
53 class MVector
54 {
55 public:
56     // constructors
57     MVector() {}
58     explicit MVector(int n) : v(n) {}
59     MVector(int n, double x) : v(n, x) {}
60     MVector(std::initializer_list<double> l) : v(l) {}
61
62     // access element (lvalue) (see example sheet 5, q5.6)
63     double &operator[](int index)
64     {
65         return v[index];
66     }
67
68     // access element (rvalue) (see example sheet 5, q5.7)
69     double operator[](int index) const {
70         return v[index];
71     }
72
73     int size() const { return v.size(); } // number of elements
74
75     // add data to your vector
76     void push_back(double x){v.push_back(x);}
77
78
79 private:
80     std::vector<double> v;
81 };
82
83 //1.2.1
84
85 inline MVector operator*(const double& lhs, const MVector& rhs)
86 {

```

```

87     MVector temp = rhs;
88     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]*=lhs;
89     return temp;
90 }
91
92 inline MVector operator*(const MVector& rhs, const double& lhs)
93 {
94     MVector temp = rhs;
95     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]*=lhs;
96     return temp;
97 }
98
99 inline MVector operator/(const MVector& rhs, const double& lhs)
100 {
101     MVector temp = rhs;
102     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]/=lhs;
103     return temp;
104 }
105
106 inline MVector operator+(const MVector& lhs, const MVector& rhs)
107 {
108     MVector temp = rhs;
109     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]=lhs[i]+rhs[i];
110     return temp;
111 }
112
113 inline MVector operator-(const MVector& lhs, const MVector& rhs)
114 {
115     MVector temp = rhs;
116     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]=lhs[i]-rhs[i];
117     return temp;
118 }
119
120 std::ostream& operator<<(std::ostream& os, const MVector& v)
121 {
122     int n = v.size();
123     os << "<<v[0]";
124     for(int i=1; i<n;i++) os<<","<<v[i];
125     os << ")";
126     return os;
127 }
128
129
130 #endif

```

5.6

```

131 #include <iostream>
132 #include "mvector.h"
133 #include <cmath>
134 #include <fstream>
135 #include <vector>
136 #include <algorithm>
137
138 // payoff function declaration
139 double Payoff_European_Call(double y, double X);
140
141 // payoff function declaration
142 double Payoff_European_Put(double y, double X);
143

```

```

144 // A function declaration
145 double A(double x, double r, double sigma, double T, double k);
146
147 // B function declaration
148 double B(double x, double y, double sigma, double T, double k);
149
150 // base integral class
151 class Integral
152 {
153     public:
154         virtual double operator()(const double& y)=0;
155         virtual double residual(const double& x, double exact)=0;
156 };
157
158 // integrate function declaration
159 double integrate(Integral &f, double a, double b, int n);
160
161 //derived test integral class
162 class Test_Integral: public Integral
163 {
164     public:
165         Test_Integral(){X=10; r=0.05; sigma=0.1;T=0.5;}
166         virtual double operator()(const double& y)
167         {
168             return X*exp(T*(y-r*sigma));
169         }
170         void SetX(double X_){X=X_;}
171         void Setr(double r_){r=r_;}
172         void Setsigma(double sigma_){sigma=sigma_;}
173         void SetT(double T_){T=T_;}
174     private:
175         double X, r, sigma, T;
176 };
177
178 // derived european option class
179 class European_Call: public Integral
180 {
181     public:
182         European_Call(){X=10; r=0.05; sigma=0.1;T=0.5; y=0.5; S_0=10;}
183         virtual double operator()(const double& y)
184         {
185             double k=(2*r)/pow(sigma,2)-1, x=std::log(S_0/X);
186             return A(x,r,sigma,T,k)*B(x,y,sigma,T,k)*Payoff_European_Call(y,X);
187         }
188         virtual double residual(const double& x, double exact)
189         {
190             sigma=x;
191             double a = -10.0;
192             double b = 10.0;
193             int n = 1000; // must be even
194             return integrate(*this, a, b, n)-exact;
195         }
196         void SetX(double X_){X=X_;}
197         void Setr(double r_){r=r_;}
198         void Setsigma(double sigma_){sigma=sigma_;}
199         void SetT(double T_){T=T_;}
200         void Sety(double y_){y=y_;}
201         void SetS_0(double S_0_){S_0=S_0_;}
202     private:
203         double X, r, sigma, T, y, S_0;
204 };

```

```

205
206 // derived european option class
207 class European_Put: public Integral
208 {
209     public:
210         European_Put(){X=10; r=0.05; sigma=0.1;T=0.5; y=0.5; S_0=10;}
211         virtual double operator()(const double& y)
212         {
213             double k=(2*r)/pow(sigma,2)-1, x=std::log(S_0/X);
214             return A(x,r,sigma,T,k)*B(x,y,sigma,T,k)*Payoff_European_Put(y,X);
215         }
216         virtual double residual(const double& x, double exact)
217         {
218             sigma=x;
219             double a = -10.0;
220             double b = 10.0;
221             int n = 1000; // must be even
222             return integrate(*this, a, b, n)-exact;
223         }
224         void SetX(double X_){X=X_;}
225         void Setr(double r_){r=r_;}
226         void Setsigma(double sigma_){sigma=sigma_;}
227         void SetT(double T_){T=T_;}
228         void Sety(double y_){y=y_;}
229         void SetS_0(double S_0_){S_0=S_0_;}
230     private:
231         double X, r, sigma, T, y, S_0;
232 };
233
234 // derived quadratic test function class
235 class Quadratic_f: public Integral
236 {
237     public:
238         Quadratic_f(){}
239         virtual double residual(const double& x, double exact)
240         {
241             exact=0;
242             return x*x-2.0-exact;
243         }
244         virtual double operator()(const double& x)
245         {
246             return x*x-2.0;
247         }
248 };
249
250 // estimates yearly variance of a stock following a log normal random walk
251 double Variance_Estimator(MVector v){
252     MVector w;
253     for (int i=1;i<v.size();i++)
254     {
255         w.push_back(std::log(v[i])-std::log(v[i-1]));
256     }
257     double sum=0, sum_of_squares=0;
258     for (int i=0;i<w.size();i++)
259     {
260         sum+=w[i];
261         sum_of_squares+=w[i]*w[i];
262     }
263     double var;
264     var=(sum_of_squares/(w.size()-1))-((sum*sum)/(w.size()*w.size()-w.size()));
265     return std::sqrt(252*var);

```

```

266 }
267
268 // function to implement Simpsons rule from y=a to y=b with n steps
269 double integrate(Integral &f, double a, double b, int n)
270 {
271     if (n%2!=0 || a>b) {std::cout<<"Error"<<std::endl; return 1;}
272     double sum=0, h=(b-a)/n;
273     sum+=f(a)+f(b);
274     for (int j=1; j<=n/2-1;j++)
275     {
276         sum+=2*f(a+2*j*h)+4*f(a+(2*j-1)*h);
277     }
278     sum=(h/3)*(sum+4*f(a+(n-1)*h));
279     return sum;
280 }
281
282
283 double Payoff_European_Call(double y, double X)
284 {
285     return std::max(X*(exp(y)-1),0.0);
286 }
287
288 double Payoff_European_Put(double y, double X)
289 {
290     return std::max(X*(1-exp(y)),0.0);
291 }
292
293 double A(double x, double r, double sigma, double T, double k)
294 {
295     return exp(-0.5*k*x-0.125*pow(sigma,2)*pow(k,2)*T-r*T)/std::sqrt(2*pow(sigma,2)*M_PI*T
296 );
297 }
298
299 double B(double x, double y, double sigma, double T, double k)
300 {
301     return exp(-pow(x-y,2)/(2*pow(sigma,2)*T)+0.5*k*y);
302 }
303 // secant method tester function
304
305 double newton_secant_f(double x) // returns f(x)
306 {
307     return x*x-2.0;
308 }
309
310 // secant iterator
311 bool NewtonSecant(Integral &f,double &result, double x0, double x1, double tol, int
312 maxiter, double exact)
313 {
314     int i;
315     double x;
316     for (i=0; i<maxiter; i++)
317     {
318         x = x1 - f.residual(x1,exact)*(x1-x0)/
319         (f.residual(x1,exact)-f.residual(x0,exact));
320         if (std::abs(f.residual(x,exact))<tol) break;
321         x0=x1;
322         x1=x;
323     }
324     result = x;
325     if (i==maxiter)

```

```

326     return false;
327 else return true;
328 }
329
330
331 int main()
332 {
333     /*
334     {
335         std::ifstream input("ezj_open_prices.txt");
336         MVector column1;
337         if (!input)
338         {
339             std::cout << "Could not open file for reading" << std::endl;
340             return 1;
341         }
342         // for (int i=0; i<5; i++)
343         while (input)
344         {
345             double x1=0;
346             if (input >> x1)
347             {
348                 column1.push_back(x1);
349             }
350         }
351         input.close();
352         std::cout<<column1.size()<<std::endl;
353         std::cout<<Variance_Estimator(column1)<<std::endl;
354     }
355     */
356
357     /* 2.3.1 test a single case:
358     {
359         std::cout.precision(16);
360         double X=10, r=0.05, sigma=0.1, T=0.5;
361         Test_Integral f;
362         int n=2;
363         std::cout<<integrate(f,0,1,n)<<std::endl;
364         std::cout<<0.5*(f(0)+4*f(0.5)+f(1))/3<<std::endl;
365         double I=((X*exp(-r*sigma*T))*(exp(T)-1))/T;
366         std::cout<<I-integrate(f,0,1,n)<<std::endl;
367     }
368     */
369
370     /* 2.3.1 error analysis:
371     {
372         double X=10, r=0.05, sigma=0.1, T=0.5;
373         double I=((X*exp(-r*sigma*T))*(exp(T)-1))/T;
374         Test_Integral f;
375         int n=2;
376         for (int i=0;i<20;i++)
377         {
378             double h=1.0/n;
379             double error_bound=(pow(T,4)*pow(h,4)*X*exp(T*(1-r*sigma)))/180;
380             std::cout.precision(16);
381             // std::cout<<integrate(f,0,1,n)<<std::endl;
382             // std::cout<<I<<std::endl;
383             // std::cout<<std::abs(I-integrate(f,0,1,n))<<std::endl;
384             std::cout<<error_bound<<std::endl;
385             n*=2;
386         }

```

```

387     }
388     */
389
390     /* multiple T
391     {
392         double X=10, r=0.05, sigma=0.1;
393         int n=10e+6;
394         Test_Integral f;
395         std::cout.precision(16);
396         for (int i=0; i<5; i++)
397         {
398             f.SetT(i/4.0);
399             std::cout<<integrate(f, 0,1,n)<<std::endl;
400             std::cout<<((X*exp(-r*sigma*(i/4.0)))*(exp(i/4.0)-1))/(i/4.0)<<std::endl;
401         }
402
403     }
404     */
405     /* Testing A,B and payoff
406     {
407         double X=10, r=0.05, sigma=0.1, T=0.5, y=0.5, S_0=10;
408         double k=(2*r)/pow(sigma,2)-1, x=std::log(S_0/X);
409         std::cout<<payoff(y,X)<<std::endl;
410         std::cout<<A(x,r,sigma,T,k)<<std::endl ;
411         std::cout<<B(x,y,sigma,T,k)<<std::endl ;
412     }
413     */
414
415     /* Testing European_Call for different n
416     {
417         European_Call f;
418         European_Put g;
419         g.Setr(0.06);
420         g.SetS_0(97);
421         g.Setsigma(0.2);
422         g.SetT(0.75);
423         g.SetX(100);
424         f.Setr(0.06);
425         f.SetS_0(97);
426         f.Setsigma(0.2);
427         f.SetT(0.75);
428         f.SetX(100);
429         double exact_value=7.369373e+0;
430         for(int n=200;n<=200;n+=200)
431             std::cout<<integrate(f,-10.0,10.0,n)<<" " <<integrate(g,-10,10,n)<<std::endl;
432     }
433     */
434
435     /* newton secant quadratic tester
436     {
437         Quadratic_f f;
438         double guess=-1.5;
439         std::cout<<NewtonSecant(f,guess,guess,guess+0.5,1e-6,2,0)<<std::endl;
440         std::cout<<guess<<std::endl;
441     }
442     */
443
444     /* newton secant call tester
445     {
446         European_Call f;
447         double guess=0.5;

```

```

448     double exact=1.425;
449     f.Setr(0.002);
450     f.SetS_0(30.23);
451     f.SetT(0.1205);
452     f.SetX(29);
453     std::cout<<NewtonSecant(f, guess, guess, guess+0.1, 1e-8, 5, exact)<<std::endl;
454     std::cout<<guess<<std::endl;
455
456     for(int i=1;i<=30;i++)
457     {
458         f.Setsigma(i/100.0);
459         std::cout<<integrate(f,-10, 10, 10000)-exact<<std::endl;
460     }
461 }
462 */
463
464 /* newton secant call tester with X variation
465 {
466     European_Call f;
467     double guess=0.5;
468     double exact=1.425;
469     f.Setr(0.002);
470     f.SetS_0(30.23);
471     f.SetT(0.1205);
472     f.SetX(29);
473     std::cout<<NewtonSecant(f, guess, guess, guess+0.1, 1e-8, 5, exact)<<std::endl;
474     std::cout<<guess<<std::endl;
475     for(int i=0;i<=100;i++)
476     {
477         f.SetX(29+i/10.0);
478         NewtonSecant(f, guess, guess, guess+0.1, 1e-8, 10, exact);
479         std::cout<<guess<<std::endl;
480     }
481 }
482 */
483
484 /* newton secant call finder
485 {
486     European_Call f;
487     double guess=0.5;
488     double exact=0.05;
489     f.Setr(0.05);
490     f.SetS_0(1.0);
491     f.SetT(0.5);
492     f.SetX(1);
493     std::cout<<NewtonSecant(f, guess, guess, guess+0.1, 1e-8, 5, exact)<<std::endl;
494     std::cout<<guess<<std::endl;
495 }
496 */
497
498
499
500 /* amazon implied
501 {
502     European_Call f;
503     double guess=2;
504     double exact=(104.25+105.8)/2.0;
505     f.Setr(0.04);
506     f.SetS_0(104.55);
507     f.SetT(1.0/365.0);
508     f.SetX(130);

```

```
509     std::cout<<NewtonSecant(f, guess, guess, guess+0.1, 1e-8, 10, exact)<<std::endl;
510     std::cout<<guess<<std::endl;
511 }
512 */
513 // error investigation
514 {
515     European_Call f;
516     double guess=0.5;
517     double exact=1.425;
518     f.Setr(0.002);
519     f.SetS_0(30.23);
520     f.SetT(0.1205);
521     f.SetX(29);
522     std::cout<<NewtonSecant(f, guess, guess, guess+0.1, 1e-8, 5, exact)<<std::endl;
523     std::cout<<guess<<std::endl;
524     double limit=706;
525     std::cout<<integrate(f,-limit, limit, limit*100)-exact<<std::endl;
526 }
527
528     return 0;
529 }
```
